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FEATURES OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN NONSPECIFIC INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to identifying the features of high-resolution computed tomography in nonspecific interstitial pneumonia. According to the results of the study, radiation signs of pathology: widespread or local decrease in the transparency of the lungs, increased pattern of the lungs up to impairment, focal pneumosclerosis. To determine the nature of the lung damage, a high-resolution computed tomography of the chest organs was performed to confirm or exclude the disease. In all cases, in patients with nonspecific interstitial pneumonia, radiation methods make it possible to distinguish a wide range of pathology and, taking into account anamnesis data, the results of laboratory and instrumental research methods, made it possible to accurately determine the diagnosis according to the course - mild (cellular type), moderate (mixed type) and severe (fibrous type).

Key words: nonspecific interstitial pneumonia, types of course, diagnosis, radiation research methods.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ТОМОГРАФИИ ВЫСОКОГО РАЗРЕШЕНИЯ ПРИ НЕСПЕЦИФИЧЕСКОЙ ИНТЕРСТИЦИАЛЬНОЙ ПНЕВМОНИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена выявлению особенностям компьютерной томографии высокого разрешения при неспецифической интерстициальной пневмонии. По результатам исследования лучевые признаки патологии: распространенное или локальное снижение прозрачности легких, усиление рисунка легких вплоть до наруждения, очаговый пневмосклероз. Для определения характера поражения легких проведена компьютерная томография органов грудной клетки высокого разрешения, позволяющая подтвердить или исключить заболевание. Во всех случаях у больных неспецифической интерстициальной пневмонией лучевые методы позволяют различить широкий спектр патологии и с учетом данных анамнеза, результатов лабораторных

и инструментальных методов исследования, позволили точно определить диагноз по течению - легкое (клеточный тип), среднее (смешанный тип) и тяжелое (фиброзный тип).

Ключевые слова: неспецифическая интерстициальная пневмония, виды течения, диагностика, лучевые методы исследования.

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NOSPETSIFIK INTERSTITSINAL PNEVMONIYADA YUQORI ANIQLIKDAGI KOMPYUTER TOMOGRAFIYA XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola nospetsifik interstitsinal pnevmoniyada yuqori aniqlikdagi kompyuter tomografik xususiyatlarini aniqlashga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra patologiyaning nurli belgilari: o'pka shaffofligining keng tarqalganligi yoki mahalliy susayishi, o'pka manzarasini uning buzilishiga qadar kuchayishi, o'choqli pnevmoskleroz. O'pka zararlanish tabiatini aniqlash uchun ko'krak qafasi a'zolarining yuqori aniqlikdagi kompyuter tomografiyasi bajarildi, bu esa kasallikni tasdiqlash yoki istisno qilish imkonini beradi. Barcha holatlarda, nospetsifik interstitsinal pnevmoniya guruhidagi bemorlarda nurli usullar kasalliklarning keng doirasini farqlash va anamnez ma'lumotlarini, laborator va instrumental tekshirish usullari natijalarini hisobga olgan holda, engil (hujayra turi), o'rta (aralash turi) va og'ir kechishi (fibrozli turi) tashxisini aniq belgilashga imkon berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: nospetsifik interstitsinal pnevmoniya, kechish turlari, diagnostika, nurli tekshirish usullari.

Kirish. Hozirgi vaqtda bir qator mahalliy va xorijiy tadqiqotchilarning respirator kasalliklarni o'z vaqtida tashxislash va davolash muammosiga qiziqishi keskin oshdi [1,4]. Ayniqsa, paydo bo'layotgan koronavirus pandemiyasi muammosi nuqtai nazaridan, nafas olish yo'llarining shikastlanishi tufayli interstitsial pnevmoniyaning og'ir shakli rivojlanishi tufayli o'lim sodir bo'ladi. "Interstitsial o'pka kasalliklari" kasalliklar guruhini belgilash uchun dunyodagi eng keng tarqalgan atamadir [6,8]. Ushbu tushunchaa o'pka to'qimalarining interstitsiyning ustun zararlanishini, patologik jarayonda havo yo'llarining tez-tez ishtirok etishini nazarda tutadi. "O'pkaning diffuz parenximal kasalliklari" - parenxima zararlanishiga, ya'ni alveolitga urg'udir. Interstitsial o'pka kasalliklarini etiologiyasi ma'lum, kelib chiqishi noma'lum va ikkilamchi tizimli kasalliklarga bo'lish mumkin [2,3,9].

Shuning uchun nospetsifik interstitsinal pnevmoniyada (NIP) xarakterli rentgenologik belgilarini aniqlash, shuningdek, ushbu taqdimot asosida differentsial mezonlarni yaratish, ularni davolash va ikkilamchi profilaktika taktikasini tanlash, qisqa muddatli va uzoq muddatli prognozni aniqlash, klinik va epidemiologik tadqiqotlar davomida standartlashtirish uchun juda muhim vositadir [5,7,10].

Tadqiqot maqsadi – nospetsifik interstitsinal pnevmoniyada yuqori aniqlikdagi kompyuter tomografik xususiyatlarini aniqlash.

Tadqiqot materiali va uslublari. Material sifatida Samarqand shahar tibbiyot birlashmasining pulmonologiya bo'limiga yotqizilgan nospesifik interstitsial pnevmoniya bilan kasallangan 140 nafar bemorning tibbiy hujjatlarini retrospektiv tahlil qildik. Barcha bemorlar XKT-10 ga muvofiq umumiy klinik tekshiruvdan o'tdilar, bundan tashqari, barcha bemorlar rentgenografiya va yuqori aniqlikdagi kompyuter tomografiyasidan o'tkazildi. Tadqiqot natijalarini hisoblash va baholash Windows operatsion tizimiga ega kompyuterda MS Excel (Microsoft) dasturiy paketi, statistik ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash paketi SPSS 12.0.2 va Statistica, 6.0 (Stat Soft) yordamida amalga oshirildi. Olingan raqamli qiymatlar o'zgaruvchanlik statistikasi usullari bilan qayta ishlandi.

Tadqiqot natijalari va ularning muhoqamasi. O'pkadagi patologik o'zgarishlar, hajmi va avjlanishini aniqlash maqsadida, bemorlarga ko'krak qafasi a'zolarining yuqori aniqlikdagi kompyuter tomografiyasi (YuAKT) bajarildi.

Natijalariga ko'ra, o'pkada qo'yidagilar aniqlandi: a) hiral shisha joylari; b) infiltratsiyani mezenximal, bronxoalveolyar, plevropnevmonik turi; d) segmentar, segment osti atelektazlar; e) bullyoz, panatsinar, bo'lak markazi, paraseptal emfizema; f) distal bronxiolalarning Y-simonligi; g) bronxoektazlar, bronxioloektazlar; h) peribronxovaskulyar qoplamalar; i) bo'laklararo, bo'laklarichi interstitsiyini kuchayishi; j) pnevmofibrozo, pnevmoskleroz o'zgarishlari.

Shubhasiz, bemorlarning yoshini hisobga olgan holda, NIPEK (NIP engil kechishi) bilan og'rigan bemorlarda ko'krak qafasi a'zolari YuAKT natijalari 1-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan bo'lib, undan ko'rinib turibdiki, NIPEK bilan og'rigan bemorlarning aksariyatida (n=13) tarqalgan «hiral oyna» joylari, o'pka to'qimalarining interstitsial turidagi infiltratsiyasi aniqlangan. Emfizematoz joylari (2 bemorda bo'lak markazi emfizemasi) plevra osti zichlanish o'choqlari (n=5) bilan almashildi. 7 bemorda bo'laklarichi interstitiumning ko'chayishi kuzatildi, 6 holatda - bronxiolalarning Y-shaklidagi tuzilmalari (1-rasm).

1-rasm. NIPEK bilan og'rigan U. Bemorning, 57 yosh, ko'krak qafasining YuAKT

1-jadval.

YuAKT bo'yicha NIP bo'lgan bemorlarda rentgenologik ko'rinishlar

Rentgenologik ko'rinishlar		Asosiy (n=140)			Taqqoslash(GK va YuIK)
		NIPEK (n=16)	NIPO'K (n=59)	NIPOK (n=65)	
«Hiral oyna» joylari, Interstitsial infiltratsiya turi	abs.	13	43	45	3
	%	81,25	72,88	69,23	10,0*
Bronxoalveolyar infiltratsiya turi	abs.				12
	%				40,0
Plevropnevmonik infiltratsiya turi	abs.				
Subsegmentar, segmentar atelektazlar	abs.	2	10	12	2
	%	12,5	16,95	18,46	6,67
Sentrilobulyar emfizema	abs.	2	13	15	3
	%	15,5 ^x	22,03	23,07 ^x	10,0**
Panlobulyar emfizema	abs.		28	31	
	%		47,46 ^x	47,69 ^x	
Paraseptal emfizema	abs.				6
	%				20,0**
Bullyoz emfizema	abs.		3	4	
	%		5,08	6,15	
Bronxoektazlar, bronxioloektazlar	abs.	2	10	12	2
	%	12,5	16,95	18,46	6,67***
Peribronxial qoplamalar	abs.	6	18	20	10
	%	37,5	30,5	30,77	33,33
	abs.		10	12	4

bo'laklararo interstitsiyni kuchayishi	%		16,95	18,46	13,33
bo'laklarichi interstitsiyni kuchayishi	abs.	7	5	5	2
	%	43,75	8,47	7,69	6,67
Y- tuzilmali bronxiolalar	abs.	6			
	%	37,5			
Ifodalangan cheklangan pnevmofibrozi, subplevral zichlanish o'choqlari	abs.	5	23	25	4
	%	31,25	38,98	41,54	13,33
Diffuz pnevmoskleroz, «ari uyali o'pka» tasviri	abs.		4	6	
	%		6,77	9,23	

Izoh: Asosiy guruh va taqqoslash guruhi: * - $p < 0,001$; ** - $p < 0,01$; *** - $p < 0,05$.

NIPEK bilan og'riqan bemorlar guruhida 13 bemorda interstitsial infiltratsiya turi, asosan o'pkaning markaziy qismlarida "hiral oyna" joylari, shuningdek, 2 bemorda markazlashtirilgan emfizema qayd etilgan. Boshqa o'zgarishlar kamroq: 7 tasida bo'laklarichi interstitsiyni kuchayishi, 6 tada peribronxial qoplamalar, 2 tada subsegmentar atelektazlar. O'choqli pnevmofibrozi NIPO'K li (NIP o'rta kechishi) 23 bemorda va NIPOK li 25 bemorda aniqlangan (2-rasm).

2-rasm. NIPO'K bilan og'riqan B. bemorning, 64 yosh, ko'krak qafasining YuAKT.

NIPOK(NIP og'ir kechishi) bo'lgan 45 bemorda interstitsial infiltratsiya turi, "hiral oyna" joylari ham qayd etilgan, ular tarqoq xarakterga ega. 4 nafar bemorda bullyoz emfizema, 31 nafar bemorda panlobulyar emfizema aniqlangan. 12 tasida o'pkalarning o'rta va pastki sohalarida bo'laklararo mezenximani kuchayishi, pnevmofibrozi, zichlanish o'choqlari kuzatildi, ayrim keksa yoshlilarda «ari uyali o'pka» manzarasini shakllanishi aniqlandi.

Shunday qilib, ko'krak qafasi a'zolarining YuAKT natijalariga ko'ra, 101 (72,14%) bemorda o'pka to'qimalarining stromal infiltratsiyasi aniqlangan. NIPO'K li bemorlarda ko'proq o'pkaning markaziy qismlarida joylashgan "hiral oyna" manzaralari kuzatilgan; NIPEK va NIPOK bo'lgan bemorlarda "hiral oyna" zonalari keng tarqalgan. NIP bo'lgan barcha asosiy guruhlarda (12,14%, n=17) bo'laklarichi interstitiumning kuchayishi aniqlandi. Faqat NIPO'K va NIPOK bo'lgan bemorlarda bo'laklararo interstitsiy ko'proq darajada kuchaygan (15,71%, n=22). 63,57% hollarda (n=89) o'pkada markazlashtirilgan va panlobulyar emfizema aniqlangan, NIP bo'lgan barcha guruhlarda esa faqat sentrilobulyar emfizema, NIPO'K va NIPOKda esa panlobulyar emfizema ham kuzatilgan. Shuningdek, NIPning oxirgi 2 guruhida (5,0%) bullyoz emfizema aniqlangan. Tekshirilayotgan bemorlarning 17,14% subsegmentar atelektazlar kuzatildi (NIPEK bilan 2 bemor, NIPO'K bilan 10 va NIPOK bilan 12 bemor). Bronxiolalarning Y-shaklidagi tuzilmalari (37,5%, n=6), faqat NIPEK bilan og'riqan bemorlarda aniqlangan. Ko'krak qafasining tekshiruvi natijalariga ko'ra o'pka to'qimalarida aniq fibrosklerotik o'zgarishlar asosiy guruhdagi 53 (37,85%) bemorlarda

aniqlangan va NIPOK bilan og‘rigan bemorlarda (41,54%, n=25) ko‘proq uchraydi. Faqat oxirgi NIP guruhlaridagi 10 (7,14%) bemorlarda, diffuz pnevmofibrozni "ari yuali o‘pka" oqibatiga o‘tishi kuzatilgan.

Taqqoslash guruhida (gipertoniya kasalligi (GK) va yurak ishemik kasalligi (YuIK)) ko‘pincha bronxoalveolyar infiltratsiya turi (40,0%, n=12), o‘pka to‘qimalari infiltratsiyasining stromal turi 3 (10,0%) ta bemorda aniqlangan. 10,0% hollarda (n=3) sentrilobulyar emfizema aniqlangan. 13,33% hollarda (n=4) bo‘laklararo interstitsiyini kuchayishi kuzatildi. Peribronxial qoplamalar 10 (33,3%) bemorda qayd etilgan (3-rasm). O‘choqli pnevmofibroz 13,33% hollarda (n=4) kuzatilgan.

NIPEK (n = 16) bilan og‘rigan bemorlarda va taqqoslash guruhidagi GK va YuIK bo‘lgan bemorlarda (n = 30) tomogrammalardagi o‘zgarishlarni solishtirsak, asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarda ishonchli darajada tez-tez, «hiralı oyna» maydonlarni (p=0,001; 81,25%, n=13 va 10,0%, n=3 mos) va emfizematoz havoli shish (p=0,001; 15,5%, n=2 va 6,67%, n=2 mos) topiladi. Infiltrativ va peribronxial qoplamalar ko‘proq NIPEK li bemorlarda va taqqoslash guruhida aniqlandi (p=0,001; p=0,01 mos).

NIPO‘K (n=59) va NIPOK (n=65) li bemorlarda ko‘proq (72,88%, n=43) va (69,23%, n=45), GK va YuIK (n=30) li bemorlarga (10,0%, n=3) nisbatan, tomir-mezenximal manzaraning kuchayishi kuzatildi (p=0,001). Taqqoslangan guruhdagi bemorlarda (30,64%, n=38) o‘choqli/infiltrativ o‘zgarishlar sezilarli darajada ko‘p (p=0,001) kuzatilgan.

3-rasm - Surunkali bronxit bilan og‘rigan H. bemor, 19 yosh, YuAKTsi.

Demak, NIP li bemorlar guruhida o‘pka to‘qimalari infiltratsiyasining asosiy turi mezenximaldir. "Hiralı oyna" manzarasi nospetsifik belgi bo‘lib, jarayonni avjlanish darajasini tavsiflaydi, ko‘proq asosiy guruhlardagi 101 (72,14%) bemorda aniqlangan (p=0,001). NIPEK li bemorlarda ko‘proq o‘pkaning markaziy qismlarida "hiralı oyna" tasviri kuzatiladi (p<0,01). NIPO‘K va NIPOK li bemorlarda "hiralı oyna" maydonlar keng tarqalgan bo‘lib, NIPEK da ko‘pincha o‘pkaning bazal va orqabazal qismlarida joylashgan.

NIPEK li bemorlarda (43,75%, n=7), NIPO‘K va NIPOK li guruhlariga nisbatan, ko‘proq darajada bo‘laklarichi interstitsiyning kuchayishi aniqlandi. NIPO‘K va NIPOK li bemorlarda bo‘laklararo interstitsiy kuchaygan.

Asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarda emfizematoz havoli shishlar ishonchli darajada ko‘proq kuzatilgan (p=0,001). Bundan tashqari, kompyuter tomografiyasida emfizematoz shish paydo bo‘lgan joylar NIPEK uchun eng tipik hisoblanadi (p=0,01). 63,57% hollarda (n=89) o‘pkada markazlashtirilgan va panlobulyar emfizema aniqlangan, NIP li barcha guruhlarda esa faqat sentrilobulyar emfizema, NIPO‘K va NIPOKda esa panlobulyar emfizema ham kuzatilgan.

Tomogrammalarda bronxoektazlar/bronxioloektazlar asosiy guruhdagi barchasida yorqin ifodalangan (17,14%, n=24). NIPEK guruhini 8,33% hollarida ekspirator sinamalar paytida havo tutqichining alomati aniqlangan.

Faqat NIPEK li bemorlarda bronxiolalarning Y-shaklidagi tuzilmalari (37,5%, n=6) kuzatilgan.

Ko'krak qafasi a'zolarining natijalariga ko'ra, o'pka to'qimasida yorqin fibrozli o'zgarishlar 53 tasida (37,86%) aniqlangan va foizda ko'proq NIPEK li bemorlarda uchraydi. Olingan ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, NIPOK (41,54%) li bemorlar uchun, mayda havo yo'llarini zararlanishi, bronxlar atrofi sklerozi va periferik bronxlar tirkishi torayishi xosdir. Tomogrammalarda plevra osti joylashgan zichlashish o'choqlari NIPO'K va NIPOKga nisbatan, asosan NIPEK li bemorlarda aniqroq ifodalangan. Diffuz pnevmofibrozoqibati "ari uyasi o'pkasi" ga utishi, faqat NIPning so'nggi guruhlaridagi 10 (7,14%) bemorlarda kuzatilgan, bu o'pka arxitektonikasining nozik to'rli qayta tuzilishi bilan tavsiflanadi.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, NIPning rentgenologik belgilari: o'pka shaffofligining keng tarqalganligi yoki mahalliy susayishi, o'pka manzarasini uning buzilishiga qadar kuchayishi, o'choqli pnevmoskleroz. O'pka zararlanish tabiatini aniqlash uchun ko'krak qafasi a'zolarining YuAKT bajarildi, bu esa NIPni tasdiqlash yoki istisno qilish imkonini beradi. Barcha holatlarda, NIP guruhidagi bemorlarda YuAKT kasalliklarning keng doirasini farqlash va anamnez ma'lumotlarini, laborator va instrumental tekshirish usullari natijalarini hisobga olgan holda, NIPEK (hujayra turi), NIPO'K (aralash turi) va "NIPOK" (fibrozli turi) tashxisini aniq belgilashga imkon berdi.

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